

THE IMPORTANCE OF ENHANCING STUDENT ENGAGEMENT THROUGH PERSON-CENTERED EDUCATION IN TEACHING BIOETHICS

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ABSTRACT

The fact that the majority of graduates from these educational institutions are admitted to higher education institutions through entrance exams in their chosen specialties serves as evidence for our statement. In addition to working with gifted students, there are also subjects that provide in-depth knowledge, such as bioethics, as well as special classes and forms like tutoring (individual supplementary education). These allow students to gain broader and deeper knowledge, skills, and competencies in the subjects they are interested in.

Keywords: Students' bioethics.

Pedagogical scientists have developed substantiated pedagogical technologies for a person-centered approach in the educational process, which include: person-centered education; collaborative pedagogy; adaptive communication pedagogical technology; game technology; developmental teaching technology; problem-based learning technology; differentiated learning; and individualized learning technology.

In each of these areas, education is organized taking into account the interests, abilities, opportunities, and conditions of the student's personality. Particularly, in person-centered education, special emphasis is placed on developing the student's ability to strive for solutions to problematic situations through independent thinking.

It is important to instill in students the understanding that they should first attempt to study independently and try to solve problems in difficult learning situations without the teacher's help, and only then turn to the teacher for assistance to verify the correctness of their conclusions.

When it comes to lessons that are not mandatory depending on the interests of students, there is no room for objection that the problem-based teaching method is appropriate. In ordinary lessons, the teacher's task is often ineffective and compelling. It is important to remember that students' boredom in lessons stems not from their laziness, but from the teacher's inability to interest them in the topic being taught. Many lessons are usually conducted according to the "survey-explanation - consolidation of acquired knowledge - homework" scheme. As a result, some students' minds and hands become free.

Deviating from the lesson's objective, engaging in unnecessary conversations with students, wasting time, and failing to read supplementary literature beyond the textbook are factors that negatively impact the lesson's content. Additionally, posing overly difficult or convoluted questions can make students uncomfortable, ultimately leading to their disengagement from both the subject and the teacher.

It is particularly important to emphasize that the intensive personal development through education and upbringing, as well as the assimilation of material and spiritual values, occurs solely as a result of an individual's personal activity.

The following recommendations are considered crucial in student-centered education:

1. Determining measures for improving educational institutions' activities and effectively utilizing social, material-technical, pedagogical, and psychological resources that contribute to enhancing their efficiency.
2. Studying the accumulated experience in identifying and developing children's potential in educational institutions of developed foreign countries, as well as the republic, and applying it to the continuous education system, taking into account national and regional characteristics.
3. Developing the content and practical foundations of management and pedagogical processes that ensure the effectiveness of educational institutions specializing in teaching gifted children, based on advanced approaches.
4. Establishing cooperation between educational institutions and families to effectively educate gifted children.
5. Intensifying the development of methodological recommendations and manuals that serve to increase the effectiveness of educational institutions specializing in teaching gifted students.

In implementing these processes, alongside improving educational content and developing manuals and recommendations, introducing innovative approaches aimed at activating the educational process is of particular importance. While the initial stage of educational reforms in our republic focused on creating scientific and theoretical foundations of pedagogical technologies based on local characteristics, today these are finding practical application in the lessons of every educational institution and teacher. During our research, we identified and observed elements of pedagogical technology such as problem-based learning, integrated learning, modular learning, developmental learning, differentiated learning, active learning, and game-based learning. Among these advanced pedagogical technology approaches, active teaching methods aroused our greatest interest.

To address the issue under consideration in secondary specialized and higher education, it is advisable to use active forms and methods such as research, debates, and mutual knowledge exchange, along with increasing the educational effectiveness of information. These approaches teach students to independently discover new knowledge and concepts, defend their views and ideas, and share their worldviews and insights with their peers. This process requires fostering creative thinking, developing imagination, embracing diverse thoughts and perspectives, honing observation skills, strengthening memory, and cultivating resourcefulness, perceptiveness, ingenuity, and intelligence.

The main direction in developing independent and creative thinking in students involves fostering their ability to think independently and creatively, understand the rules and criteria for discussing specific issues, express their opinions correctly, consistently, and with proper reasoning, reflect on their thoughts, and draw conclusions from their expressed ideas.

The content of the second approach to addressing this issue is as follows:

As is known, the lesson is the primary form of organizing the educational process in educational institutions. However, most teachers perceive the main and sole purpose of the lesson they lead as "imparting knowledge to students" on the topic outlined in the work plan. In this process, the principle of unity between education and upbringing is not always observed, and in many cases, conditions for students' independent and creative thinking are not created during the lesson. For this reason, researching methods to implement topic-related knowledge in combination with activating students' independent and creative thinking during lessons is particularly relevant.

Extracurricular activities and those outside educational institutions are primarily carried out in individual, group, and mass forms. It should be emphasized that extracurricular activities not only shape the ideological foundations of students' worldviews but also ensure their transformation into practical action. In this process, a student does not remain a passive listener and observer; they begin to acquire knowledge independently and freely, strive to understand scientific and socio-political information, and become an active promoter of the qualities they have acquired among their peers.

Activities in circles and various associations aimed at students' independent and creative research, which differ in content and form, not only foster aesthetic social thinking but also lead to mutual coherence. Posing problematic issues and solving them independently and creatively helps young people acquire additional knowledge, develop their worldview, and form skills and abilities to defend their opinions with evidence.

In both directions of developing independent creative thinking among young people, the following tasks need to be addressed:

- Develop methodological foundations for enhancing independent and creative thinking skills of young people to meet globally established principles, taking into account the components of the national model of personnel training in our republic, as well as the historical formation and ethnopedagogical features of the education system;
- Develop recommendations aimed at increasing the effectiveness of general secondary education, secondary specialized education, and higher education by studying the potential for activating independent and creative thinking among young people in the subjects provided for in the curricula;
- Develop criteria for selecting the content of activities to stimulate independent and creative thinking of young people across all levels of continuous education - preschool, general secondary, secondary specialized, and higher education;
- Develop innovative technologies aimed at creating a mechanism for the rapid implementation of the most advanced practices in fostering independent and creative thinking among young people within the education system.

The recommendations presented in this regard will serve as a foundation for creating theoretical and methodological bases to increase the level of student preparation that meets the requirements of the state educational standard. This will enable students to achieve a high degree of academic mobility as highly developed individuals with active independent and creative qualities. Furthermore, to effectively address the tasks in this area, it is necessary to synthesize concepts of an independently thinking creative personality and develop information support technology for managing the process of developing its unified structure.

Conclusion: In the process of teaching specialized subjects within the education system, one of the methods for developing students' clinical thinking is the widespread application of the problem-based learning approach.

The ongoing reforms in the field of medical education in our republic constitute a process of nurturing and training bold, independent-thinking, knowledgeable, and skilled specialists who can ensure the development of Uzbekistan, contribute to its rise to the level of the world's advanced countries, as well as possess positive qualities.

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